

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

Google Scholar

SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Tursunxo'jayev Jahongir Jovdatovich

**THE WAYS TO REFLECT AFFECTIVE EMOTIONS (ANGER, JOY, HORROR,
ADMIRATION) AND THEIR EXPRESSION IN LITERARY TEXTS**

DRJI

Universal
Impact Factor

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

2023-2024

zenodo

ADVANCED SCIENCE INDEX

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ